

Safety and Ethics in Intelligent Assistive Mobility

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Abstract—In the context of Artificial Intelligence Cyber Physical Systems (AI-CPSs), the concept of ethical safety refers to all the practices aimed at ensuring safe solutions are also aligned with ethical principles. It goes beyond traditional safety assessment, which focuses on preventing potential harms and minimizing the risks, by incorporating considerations of fairness and respect for human rights. This work presents the practices followed in the H-EU project REXASI-PRO as a first example in this direction.

Index Terms—Safety, ethics, Cyber physical system, AI

I. INTRODUCTION

Safety and ethics are two deeply interconnected concepts in AI systems that highlight the importance of creating trustworthy solutions. AI systems safety assessment minimizes the risks and protects users and the environment from potential harms, while ethical assessment ensures that these AI systems respect human rights, fairness, and societal values. In this paper, we show these aspects by making reference to our ongoing Horizon Europe project, called REXASI-PRO (“REliable & eXplAinable Swarm Intelligence for People with Reduced mObility”), where a particular methodology merging safety and ethics is followed in the development of all Work Packages. Ethical, legal and social (ELS) aspects were analysed from the beginning of the work and went through all stages of development. The point of reference were the recommendations elaborated in many works of Roboethics [1], the ALTAI (Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence for self-assessment) [2], the AI ACT on risk level categorization [3], and recent studies on AI Trustworthiness applied to deep learning robots [4], [5]. In this context, safety aspects concern both the safety of the user and people in the environment, the level of risk - and the elimination of risk - and the well-being and comfort of the user, his state of control and confidence in the system.

II. REXASI-PRO USE CASE

A. System description

REXASI-PRO project’s main use case (UC) involves setting up a collaborative navigation environment constituted by four

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main components:

- 1) *Autonomous wheelchair*: after receiving a desired destination through a vocal command from the user, it is designed to safely move in indoor crowded spaces, by following an optimal global path suggested by the orchestrator. The wheelchair also features an ad-hoc neural network to control local navigation. In case of an emergency event, fail-safe plans are adopted without causing panic situations.
- 2) *Flying robot*: it creates a map of the internal empty spaces where the wheelchair will be supposed to move, and it can also work as an “emergency camera” during the wheelchair movement and help in detecting dangerous situations.
- 3) *Cameras*: positioned in strategic points, they are adopted to detect pre-determined types of events and notify the orchestrator about them.
- 4) *Orchestrator*: relying on the map generated by the drone and on the environmental information collected by both cameras and drone, it finds the best path for the wheelchair to reach its destination, also integrating further information about the status of rooms and corridors.

Tracking and AI-based object detection algorithms play an essential role in monitoring and avoiding hazardous events, such as imminent collisions, occurring in areas where the only reliance on wheelchair’s integrated sensors is not enough. An example could be a corner, as shown in Fig. 1. Through the

Fig. 1. Potentially dangerous collision in a corner with limited visibility camera installed in the corner, the approaching people, not

Malfunctioning Behaviour	Hazard Description	Mode	Speed	Visibility	Crowd Density	Potential effect	Exposure comment	E	Severity comment	S	Controllability comment	C	ASIL	Safety goal
Not detecting a person	Collision with a person	Fully autonomous mode	High	Bad visibility (e.g., smoke, reflecting surface, dark scenario)	High	Collision of the WC with persons may injure persons	Very likely if the sensors fail or are beyond their limitations	E4	A person on a wheelchair hitting an obstacle at high speed may be severely injured.	S2	Remove dead man switch in case they are afraid. This may fail in case a person cannot react under fear.	C1	ASIL-A	Have a watchdog checking availability and plausibility of sensor data

TABLE I
EXAMPLE FROM REXASI-PRO SAFETY ANALYSIS PROCEDURE.

Fig. 2. High-level overview of the safety analysis approach within REXASI-PRO framework

visible to the wheelchair, are detected and an alert message is sent to the wheelchair, which can react by stopping or slowing down.

B. Approach to safety analysis

Among the different standards and guidelines addressing the safety of autonomous systems, the ISO/PAS 21448 Safety Of The Intended Functionality (SOTIF) [6], originally from the automotive field, is particularly suitable as it explicitly tackles the presence of AI, by foreseeing that a hazard may occur even in absence of a system failure, but rather when the system faces unexpected scenarios, outside of the operational design domain (ODD). This is frequently the case of AI algorithms that, when deployed, are fed with inputs different from training, thus increasing the risk of AI failures. SOTIF's ultimate goal is thus reducing the unsafe scenarios, via proper verification and validation methods. Fig. 2 shows how SOTIF, together with principles from FMEA, IEC61508 and ISO26262 [7], is adopted for devising a suitable framework for REXASI-PRO safety analysis. The overall process involves hazards identification by analysing the limitations and/or conditions potentially leading to hazards, and evaluating their impact on the system under environmental/wheelchair-related conditions as determined by the ODD. The procedure ends up defining *safety goals*, which are the strategies adopted to address and

mitigate the potential risks identified during the analysis to ensure safe operations within the ODD.

Table I reports an example of outcome of the safety analysis process for the wheelchair. It shows the case that the wheelchair sensors fail in detecting a person moving when the operative conditions are very tough, with high speed, bad visibility and highly crowded environment. Field experts within REXASI-PRO's consortium assigned the maximum level of exposure, following the criticality of the ODD conditions that increase the hazard probability, a high level of severity, since the consequences of collisions can be severe and life-threatening, and a low controllability score (C1, simply controllable).

C. Ethical assessment

REXASI-PRO's methodological approach on ELS issues requires that each aspect concerning the safety and well-being of the system user and the people living and inhabiting the environment is discussed at every level of project development, from automatic control to the use of AI techniques applied to autonomous navigation and HMI, to the level of transparency and explainability of the AI algorithms and system behaviour. Since the system is designed to be used by people with reduced mobility, the safety goals concern both the physical safety and well-being of users and humans in the environment under foreseeable conditions as well as the possible psychological and emotional implications for the users and people in the environment in case of unexpected events. From this point of view, in cases like that of Table I, controllability scores might be increased to better take into account all such social aspects. Future developments of the project topics will investigate these cardinal connections between ethics issues and risk management as low as reasonably practicable.

III. CONCLUSIONS

Ethical safety ensures that the AI-CPS do not generate harm, discrimination and inequity for the people involved. It requires a proactive approach to identify potential ethical risks and integrating safeguards that protect against these risks while maintaining the system's overall safety and correct functionality. We reported the example of the REXASI-PRO project, where we carried out a first attempt to blend safety and ethics, thus making a first step towards a more human-centered approach to risk analysis.

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